

Antimicrobial Properties of Proton Pump Inhibitors: A Comprehensive Review

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Citation: Dr. Rohan K. Patel, Dr. Smita J. Mehta, Dr. Aaradhya S. Sheth, Dr. Tushar R. Desai (2026). Antimicrobial Properties of Proton Pump Inhibitors: A Comprehensive Review. *Psychiatry*, 18(1), 35-43. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19096820>

ABSTRACT

Proton pump inhibitors [PPI] are acid activated pro drugs which convert in to sulfenic acid and then in to tetracycline sulfenamide in the acidic pH of parietal cell canaliculi. They block H⁺K⁺ATPase proton pumps and reduce gastric acid secretion. They are used to treat acid peptic disorders and NSAID induced gastric mucosal injury. Activity of PPI against *Helicobacter pylori* [H.pylori] is proved undisputably. Lansoprazole is the most effective PPI against H.pylori due to its unique chemical structure.PPI inhibit urease activity of H. pylori. They affect respiration and energy metabolism of these organisms as result of decreased ATP synthesis. Structural similarity of benzimidazole PPI with imidazole like metronidazole and tinidazole may contribute for their antibacterial property. Omeprazole and lansoprazole have been found to have anti fungal activity by inhibition of fungal H⁺K⁺ATPase-vacuolar ATPase which are essential for fungal survival and to carry out essential physiological functions, the inhibition of which leads to fungicidal action. Recently anti tubercular action of lansoprazole was highlighted which is attributed to its intra mycobacterial sulfoxide reduction to lansoprazole sulfide. This acts on mycobacterial cytochrome bc₁ complex and inhibits ATP synthesis and compromises energy metabolism threatening its survival. Cytochrome bc₁ of plasmodium also forms a drug target for lansoprazole. Thus, lansoprazole can emerge as a potential drug to treat MDR tuberculosis and malaria. Antiviral action of lansoprazole was noted against rhinovirus. Gram positive and negative organisms other than H.pylori were found to be inhibited by omeprazole in vitro. But this is not supported by in vivo studies.

Keywords: antimicrobial, antitubercular, H pylori, proton pump inhibitors.

INTRODUCTION

Proton pump inhibitors [PPIs] are weak bases and consists of two moieties. One of it is substituted pyridine with primary pKa of about 4.0 which helps for its selective accumulation in the secretory canaliculus of parietal cells. Other being benzimidazole with second pKa of about 1.0. PPIs are acid activated pro drugs which convert in to sulfenic acid and then in to tetracyclic sulfenamide. The gastric P type parietal cell H⁺K⁺ATPase-proton pump- is the primary target for the PPIs. Activated sulfenamide react co-valently with one or more cysteine accessible from luminal surface of the ATPase. This co-valent binding makes their inhibitory effect to last longer than their plasma half life-Hit and run drugs¹⁻³.

PPIs are most commonly preferred drugs to treat acid peptic disorders like duodenal ulcer, gastric ulcer, gastro oesophageal reflux disorders and NSAID induced gastric mucosal injuries. They are used in combination with antibiotics like amoxicillin and clarithromycin in the treatment of *Helicobacter pylori* [H. pylori] infection eradication⁴. PPIs also have antioxidant⁵, anti

infection. PPIs are considered to be effective in fungal¹⁰ and viral infections¹¹. Latest evidence suggests the role of PPI like Lansoprazole in the treatment of Mycobacterium tuberculosis[MTB] infection¹².

Effect of PPIs on H. pylori infection

H. pylori is a gram negative, urease positive, curved or spiral bacterium which colonises on the human gastric mucosa and damages it by release of cytotoxins.¹³ They were first isolated by Warren and Marshall in 1983 from gastric mucosae of patients of gastritis.¹⁴ H. pylori is the principal cause of gastritis and peptic ulcer and also predisposes to gastric carcinoma¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Benzimidazole PPIs like lansoprazole and omeprazole bind to gastric parietal cell proton pumps, inhibit them and reduce gastric acid secretion¹⁸. Lansoprazole and its analogues inhibit H. pylori growth selectively. Other bacterial species are not affected by lansoprazole even at higher concentrations¹⁹.

Possible mechanisms for action of lansoprazole on H. pylori are as follows

PPI induced increase in gastric pH and reduced gastric juice volume enhances the effect of co- administered antibiotics

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inflammatory^{6,7} and anti diabetic actions⁸. PPI have been used to reduce chemoresistance in the treatment of malignancy⁹. Thus, PPIs have pleiotropic benefits. Recently their antimicrobial actions are getting highlighted. They are proved to be effective in the treatment of H. pylori

like amoxicillin and clarithromycin by increasing their concentration in the reduced gastric juice²⁰.

It is also thought that lansoprazole and omeprazole inhibit the urease activity of H. pylori. H. pylori produce large

amount of urease which help the bacterium to survive in the acidic environment of the stomach²¹.

H. pylori is a microaerophilic bacterium having strict respiratory form metabolism and also oxidizes organic acids as an energy source²². When *H. pylori* cells were incubated with lansoprazole, their cellular ATP levels were decreased in dose dependent manner. This reduction in ATP levels by lansoprazole was attributed to the inhibition of ATP synthesis as result of respiratory inhibition. Lansoprazole inhibited cellular respiration of endogenous substrate²³. *H. pylori* does not have complete tri carboxylic acid cycle²⁴. Organic acids like pyruvate, succinate, isocitrate and alpha ketoglutarate are metabolised by *H. pylori* which form the respiratory substrates²². The respiratory pathways for pyruvate or alpha ketoglutarate and succinate differ in *H. pylori*. In *H. pylori*, alpha ketoglutarate and pyruvate get dehydrogenated by different dehydrogenase system. Two step system which generate NADPH appear to be present in *H. pylori*. Alpha ketoglutarate and pyruvate may get oxidized with flavodoxin and this flavodoxin is responsible for reduction of NADP. The enzyme system corresponding to complex III is present in *H. pylori*. The main inhibitory target of lansoprazole is NADPH quinone oxidoreductase system corresponding to complex-I, though it might inhibit the ketoacid dependent NADPH reduction.²³ Pyruvate appears to be the main substrate for energy production in *H. pylori*²⁵.

Antimicrobial activity of PPI may be due their structural similarity with imidazole like metronidazole and tinidazole^{26,27}.

PPIs with substituted benzimidazole derivatives who have pyridine ring which show significant activity against *H. pylori*. But there were significant differences in their potential. This was related to their structure activity relationship. Substitution at the number 4 of pyridine ring with fluoroalkoxy exhibited several times more antibacterial activity. Presence of trifluoroethoxy group at C4 position of pyridine ring in lansoprazole makes it more potent antibacterial agent against *H. Pylori* than omeprazole. Lansoprazole was found to have no antibacterial activity against other bacteria except *H. pylori*¹⁹.

Effect of PPI on fungal infection

Candida albicans is the most frequent fungal pathogen causing hospital acquired blood stream infections²⁸. Usually it is a harmless commensal in the oral cavity, genital regions and digestive tract of healthy people and sometimes associated with superficial infections. Entry of pathogen in the blood stream is facilitated by tissue damage or by the formation of fungal biofilms on the medical implants or devices resulting into sepsis and organ failure. This is more common in immunocompromised patients or in those who are undergoing immunosuppressive therapy²⁹. *C. albicans* exists either in unicellular yeast or filamentous hyphae form. Yeast form is non pathogenic and hyphae form being virulent induces host tissue damage and invasion³⁰. Serine aspartyl proteinases and lipases secreted by *c.albicans* are involved in nutrient acquisition, immune invasion and host cell degradation³¹. Other *c. albicans* virulence pathways include iron acquisition from hemoglobin, protection against reactive oxygen species, expression of adhesion molecules and formation of biofilms. These pathways help in host cell invasion and provide protection against the host immune response³².

H^+K^+ ATPase located in the vacuolar organelle are vacuolar V-ATPases. V-ATPase pumps are molecular proton motors with multi subunits responsible for active transport of protons and hydrolysis of ATP. Energy arising out of ATP hydrolysis is needed for proton transport. This is required for acidification of intracellular compartment like golgi apparatus, endosomes and lysosomes^{33,34}. V-ATPase redistributes protons from cytosol to the acidic organelle lumen and maintain their pH homeostasis. V-ATPase also contribute to regulation of cytosolic pH in fungi³⁵. In fungi plasma membrane proton transporter Pmalp regulates cytosolic pH by pumping protons out of the cell in to the extracellular space to maintain cytosolic pH ranging from neutral to alkaline and extracellular acidic³⁶. Pmalp expression and activity gets upregulated during filamentation of fungi like *c.albicans*^{37,38} which correlates with their virulence. Germ tube formation which is the precursor step to hyphae formation needs alkaline cytoplasm^{10, 39,40}. V-ATPase is known to regulate Pmalp activity in fungi like *saccharomyces cervisiae* [*s.cervisiae*] 41,35,42.

Vacuolar pH contributes for virulence and physiological function of *c.albicans*. Maintaining proton gradient across vacuolar membrane is essential for cellular metabolism, receptor mediated endocytosis, intracellular membrane trafficking, protein degradation and pro-hormone processing. It is also responsible for the uptake of small molecules and storage and detoxification of metabolites and ions⁴³. Activation and secretion of proteinase and lipase virulence factors depends on optimal vacuolar pH³¹. Some aspartyl proteinases and lipase secreted by *c. albicans* are also involved in acquisition of nutrients, immune invasion and host cell degradation³¹. V-ATPase is highly conserved across species and best characterized in fungus like *s.cervisiae*. But mammals differ from fungi in the isoform composition of 14 sub units and in the complex disassembly regulation⁴⁴. These differences could be used for selectivity of V-ATPase as a target of antifungal drug which would not affect human V-ATPases. V-ATPase proton transport requires structural and functional coupling of domain V1 which is peripheral with the domain V0 which is embedded in the membrane^{45,34}. Various structural changes have taken place in V-ATPase from fungi to human in the process of evolution for e.g c ring of all fungal species contain three sub units V_{0c} , V_{0c}' , V_{0c}'' . But mammal c ring lacks the V_{0c}' subunit which is specifically found in fungi⁴⁶. In the process of evolution human V-ATPase have developed multiple isoforms for V1 and V0 subunits which are tissue and membrane specific^{47,48, 49}. Pharmacological inactivation of V-ATPase pumps of fungi change both extra and intracellular pH which disturbs important cellular processes like protein processing and sorting, protein secretion, zymogen activation, vesicular membrane trafficking, receptor mediated endocytosis and autophagy^{33,34}.

Thus acting on fungal V-ATPases PPI compromise on nutrition, vital physiological functions and development of virulent form of fungi resulting in to inhibition of fungal growth.

Thus, plasma membrane H^+K^+ ATPase forms a molecular target for antifungal drug therapy and inhibition of their enzyme activity correlates with cell growth inhibition. PPI like omeprazole was found to inhibit growth of *c.albicans* as a result of Inhibition of H^+K^+ ATPase^{38,50}. In

a study conducted by Sivoshi F (2012) lansoprazole showed weak fungicidal activity requiring 24 hours to reach their desired antifungal activity. Lansoprazole also had antifungal activity against *C. tropicalis* and *C. spp*⁵¹.

Anti tubercular activity of PPI

Multi drug resistant [MDR] tuberculosis is the major concern in the field of treatment of tuberculosis. Despite therapeutic advances in the treatment of tuberculosis, it continues to be the major cause of morbidity and mortality. Overall success rate in the cure of tuberculosis is not very promising [about 48%] due to lack of effective regimens, fast development of drug resistance and the failure on patients part to complete the prescribed chemotherapy of tuberculosis. Co-existing immunocompromised conditions like HIV infection complicates the prognosis⁵². Hence the drug resistant pathogens require development of newer effective drugs to overcome the resistance. Lansoprazole [LPZ], a gastric proton pump inhibitor, was found to have intracellular anti tubercular activity. LPZ is a pro drug which is relatively unstable gets converted in to its analogue lansoprazole sulfide [LPZS] intracellularly by sulfoxide reduction through enzymatic or non enzymatic reactions. LPZS is a highly stable metabolite. In conducted studies, it showed highly *M.tuberculosis* selective antimicrobial action without affecting Gram negative and Gram positive organisms. Cytochrome bc1 [complex III] is an essential respiratory chain component which is required for ATP synthesis. Ratio of ADP/ATP in LPZS treated mycobacterium was about 7 fold more than in those of LPZS untreated mycobacterium. LPZS prevents the generation of ATP from ADP by acting on bc1 cytochrome complex and thus disrupts the mycobacterial respiratory chain, challenging its viability¹². Cytochrome b subunit of the cytochrome bc1 complex-QcrB- was identified as drug target of mycobacterium tuberculosis⁵³. QcrB is a putative ubiquinol cytochrome c reductase [sub unit B] an integral member of the bc1 complex of the respiratory electron transport chain⁵⁴. QcrB forms the target protein for the action of LPZS. QcrB is an emerging, highly vulnerable target for *M.tuberculosis* and LPZS represents a novel class of QcrB inhibitors. LPZS is highly safe and promising anti tubercular lead compound which does not inhibit gastric H⁺K⁺ATPase. Thus differential pro drug activation of LPZ in gastric parietal cells [sulfenic acid and sulfenamide intermediates] and mycobacterial host cells [sulfoxide reduction of LPZ in to LPZs] makes LPZS as a novel, specific and highly effective anti tubercular drug¹². Thus targeting bc1 complex and QcrB of *M.tuberculosis* is the new mechanism of action of anti TB drugs along with existing mechanisms like inhibition of mycolic acid synthesis, arabinoglycan, DNA dependent RNA polymerase, peptide synthesis and binding to DNA gyrase. *Anti malarial action of PPIs*

Drug like atovaquone and several other anti malarial drugs target the cytochrome b of plasmodium. Despite the presence of human mitochondrial orthologues, targeting the parasitic cytochrome bc1 complex is quite safe⁵⁵. Recently it is observed that LPZ is a potent inhibitor of plasmodial growth only when they have infected metabolically active liver cells. It is likely that intracellular sulfoxide reduction results in to anti plasmodial activity⁵⁶. Thus, PPI like LPZ becomes an important pharmacological tool to control

malaria and tuberculosis, both being very important causes of mortality.

Anti viral action of PPI

When LPZ was tried on the rhinovirus infected tracheal epithelial cell culture, it inhibited this infection by reducing ICAM-1 and by reducing endogenous production of Interleukin-1 beta and also by blocking the entry of rhinovirus RNA in to endosomes¹¹. *Antibacterial action of PPIs on other bacteria* Antibacterial effect of omeprazole was observed in vitro to be more effective on the inhibition of Gram positive bacteria like enterococcus fecalis and staphylococcus aureus than on Gram negative bacteria like *E.coli* and *K.pneumoniae*⁵⁷. Variation in the action of omeprazole on these bacteria could be explained on the basis of the number or accessibility of SH group and cysteine content in them which are located in the outer membrane proteins of bacteria. Also, a degree of cysteine dependence of these bacteria governs the growth inhibition of these organisms by omeprazole⁵⁸. Antibacterial actions of PPI on other bacteria in vivo studies are not very significant.

CONCLUSION

PPI are extensively used due to their safety profile in acid peptic disorders and in NSAID induced gastro intestinal injuries. The beneficial effects of these drugs to treat *H. pylori* infection is proved beyond doubt. They also have been found to possess antifungal, antiviral and in vitro antibacterial properties. Pro drug lansoprazole gets converted in to lansoprazole sulfide within mycobacteria, which has been found to inhibit bacterial cytochrome bc1 complex, reduce ATP synthesis and affects its energy metabolism. This results in to mycobacteriocidal activity. Lansoprazole was observed to have anti plasmodial action by same mechanism as that in mycobacteria. These beneficial actions of lansoprazole on mycobacterium and plasmodium makes it a promising drug to treat MDR tuberculosis and malaria. Further studies regarding the actions of lansoprazole and its metabolites or derivatives would prove as boon in the treatment of drug resistant tuberculosis and malaria.

REFERENCES

1. Shin J, Sachs G. Pharmacology of Proton Pump Inhibitors. *Curr Gastroenterol Rep.* 2008; 10(6): 528–534.
2. Shin J, Munson K, Vagin O, Sachs G. The gastric HKATPase: structure, function, and inhibition. *Pflugers Arch.* 2009; 457(3): 609–622.
3. Sachs G, Shin J, Vagin O, Lambrecht N, Yakubov I, Munson K. The Gastric H,K ATPase as a Drug Target Past, Present, and Future. *J Clin Gastroenterol.* 2007; 41(Suppl 2): S226–S242.
4. Nagata K, Sone N, Tamura T. Inhibitory activities of lansoprazole against respiration in *Helicobacter pylori*. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 2001 May;45(5):1522–7.
5. Becker JC, Grosser N, Waltke C, Schulz S, Erdmann K, Domschke W, et al.. Beyond gastric acid reduction: proton pump inhibitors induce heme oxygenase-1 in gastric and endothelial cells. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun.* 2006;345(3):1014–21.
6. Ichikawa H, Yoshida N, Takagi T, Tomatsuri N, Katada K, Isozaki Y, et al. Lansoprazole ameliorates intestinal

- mucosal damage induced by ischemiareperfusion in rats. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2004;10(19):2814-7.
7. Kuroda M, Yoshida N, Ichikawa H, Takagi T, Okuda T, Naito Y, et al. Lansoprazole, a proton pump inhibitor, reduces the severity of indomethacin-induced rat enteritis. *Int J Mol Med.* 2006; 17(1):89-93.
 8. González-Ortiz M, Martínez-Abundis E, MercadoSesma AR, Álvarez-Carrillo R. Effect of pantoprazole on insulin secretion in drug-naïve patients with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract.* 2015;108(1):e11-3.
 9. Yeo M, Kim DK, Kim YB, Oh TY, Lee JE, Cho SW, et al. Selective induction of apoptosis with proton pump inhibitor in gastric cancer cells. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2004;10(24):8687-96.
 10. Mahanty SK, Gupta P, Banerjee U, Fotedar R, Prasad R. Defective plasma membrane H(+)-ATPase or orthovanadate resistant mutants from *Candida albicans*, a pathogenic yeast. *Biochem Int.* 1990;22(1):11-20.
 11. Sasaki T, Yamaya M, Yasuda H, Inoue D, Yamada M, Kubo H, et al. The proton pump inhibitor lansoprazole inhibits rhinovirus infection in cultured human tracheal epithelial cells. *Eur J Pharmacol.* 2005;509(2-3):20110.
 12. Rybniker J, Vocat A, Sala C, Busso P, Pojer F, Benjak A et al. Lansoprazole is an antituberculous prodrug targeting cytochrome bc1. *Nature Communications* 2015; 6: 7659.
 13. Blaser MJ. *Helicobacter pylori* and the pathogenesis of gastroduodenal inflammation. *J Infect Dis.* 1990;161(4):626-33.
 14. Warren J, Marshall B. Unidentified curved bacilli on gastric epithelium in active chronic gastritis. *The lancet* Volume 1983; 321: 1273–1275.
 15. Parsonnet J, Friedman GD, Vandersteen DP, Chang Y, Vogelman JH, Orentreich N, et al. *Helicobacter pylori* infection and the risk of gastric carcinoma. *N Engl J Med.* 1991; 325(16):1127-31.
 16. Parsonnet J, Hansen S, Rodriguez L, Gelb AB, Warnke RA, Jellum E, et al. *Helicobacter pylori* infection and gastric lymphoma. *N Engl J Med.* 1994;330(18):126771.
 17. Rabeneck Linda R, Ransohoff D. Is *Helicobacter pylori* a cause of duodenal ulcer? A methodologic critique of current evidence. *The American journal of medicine,* 1991; 91: 566–572.
 18. Fellenius E, Berglindh T, Sachs G, Olbe L, Elander B, Sjöstrand SE, et al. Substituted benzimidazoles inhibit gastric acid secretion by blocking (H⁺ + K⁺)ATPase. *Nature.* 1981; 290(5802):159-61.
 19. Iwahi T, Satoh H, Nakao M, Iwasaki T, Yamazaki T, Kubo K, et al. Lansoprazole, a novel benzimidazole proton pump inhibitor, and its related compounds have selective activity against *Helicobacter pylori*. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 1991;35(3):490-6.
 20. Kawano S, Murakami M, Saita H, Tsuji S. Effect of lansoprazole in mono-, dual-, or triple therapy on *Helicobacter pylori* eradication. *J Gastroenterol.* 1996; 31: 41-3.
 21. Nagata K, Satoh H, Iwahi T, Shimoyama T, Tamura T. Potent inhibitory action of the gastric proton pump inhibitor lansoprazole against urease activity of *Helicobacter pylori*: unique action selective for *H. pylori* cells. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 1993;37(4):769-74.
 22. Kelly D. The Physiology and Metabolism of the Human Gastric Pathogen *Helicobacter pylori*. *Advances in Microbial Physiology.* 1998; 40: 137–189.
 23. Nagata K, Sone N, Tamural T. Inhibitory Activities of Lansoprazole against Respiration in *Helicobacter pylori*. *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.* 2001; 45: 51522-152.
 24. Tomb JF, White O, Kerlavage AR, Clayton RA, Sutton GG, Fleischmann RD, et al. The complete genome sequence of the gastric pathogen *Helicobacter pylori*. *Nature.* 1997; 388(6642):539-47.
 25. Mendz GL, Hazell SL, van Gorkom L. Pyruvate metabolism in *Helicobacter pylori*. *Arch Microbiol.* 1994;162(3):187-92.
 26. Nakao M. Antibacterial properties of lansoprazole alone and in combination with antimicrobial agents against *Helicobacter pylori*. *J Clin Gastroenterol.* 1995;20 Suppl 1:S32-7.
 27. Sjøstrøm J E, Kühler T, Larsson H. Basis for the selective antibacterial activity in vitro of proton pump inhibitors against *Helicobacter* spp. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 1997; 41(8): 1797–1801.
 28. Klotz SA, Chasin BS, Powell B, Gaur NK, Lipke PN. Polymicrobial bloodstream infections involving *Candida* species: analysis of patients and review of the literature. *Diagn Microbiol Infect Dis.* 2007; 59(4):401-6.
 29. Pfaller MA, Diekema DJ. Epidemiology of invasive candidiasis: a persistent public health problem. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 2007; 20(1):133-63.
 30. Sudbery P. Growth of *Candida albicans* hyphae. *Nature Reviews Microbiology* 2011; 9: 737-748.
 31. Naglik JR, Challacombe SJ, Hube B. *Candida albicans* secreted aspartyl proteinases in virulence and pathogenesis. *Microbiol Mol Biol Rev.* 2003;67(3):400-28.
 32. Karkowska-Kuleta J, Rapala-Kozik M, Kozik A. Fungi pathogenic to humans: molecular bases of virulence of *Candida albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*. *Acta Biochim Pol.* 2009;56(2):211-24.
 33. Kane PM. The where, when, and how of organelle acidification by the yeast vacuolar H⁺-ATPase. *Microbiol Mol Biol Rev.* 2006;70(1):177-91.
 34. Forgac, M. Vacuolar ATPases: Rotary proton pumps in physiology and pathophysiology, *Nat. Rev. Mol. Cell Biol.* 2007; 8: 917–929.
 35. Martínez-Muñoz G, Kane P. Vacuolar and Plasma Membrane Proton Pumps Collaborate to Achieve Cytosolic pH Homeostasis in Yeast *The Journal of Biological Chemistry.* 2008; 283: 20309-20319.
 36. Monk B C, Kurtz M B, Marrinan J A, Perlin D S. Cloning and characterization of the plasma membrane H(+)-ATPase from *Candida albicans*. *J. Bacteriol.* 1991; 173:216826-6836.
 37. Kaur S, Mishra P. Dimorphism-associated changes in plasma membrane H(+)-ATPase activity of *Candida albicans*. *Arch Microbiol.* 1991;156:412-5.
 38. Monk BC, Niimi M, Shepherd MG. The *Candida albicans* plasma membrane and H(+)-ATPase during yeast growth and germ tube formation. *J Bacteriol.* 1993; 175(17): 5566–5574.

39. Stewart E, Gow NA, Bowen DV. Cytoplasmic alkalinization during germ tube formation in *Candida albicans*. *J Gen Microbiol*. 1988;134(5):1079-87.
40. Stewart EI, Hawser S, Gow NA. Changes in internal and external pH accompanying growth of *Candida albicans*: studies of non-dimorphic variants. *Arch Microbiol*. 1989;151(2):149-53.
41. Perzov N, Nelson H, Nelson N. Altered distribution of the yeast plasma membrane H⁺-ATPase as a feature of vacuolar H⁺-ATPase null mutants. *J Biol Chem*. 2000; 275(51): 40088-95.
42. Huang C, Chang A. pH-dependent Cargo Sorting from the Golgi. *J Biol Chem*. 2011; 286(12): 10058–10065.
43. Veses V, Richards A, Gow NA. Vacuoles and fungal biology. *Curr Opin Microbiol*. 2008;11(6):503-10.
44. Hayek SR, Lee SA, Parra KJ. Advances in targeting the vacuolar proton-translocating ATPase (V-ATPase) for anti-fungal therapy. *Front Pharmacol*. 2014;5:4.
45. Sun-Wada GH, Wada Y, Futai M. Vacuolar H⁺ pumping ATPases in luminal acidic organelles and extracellular compartments: common rotational mechanism and diverse physiological roles. *J Bioenerg Biomembr*. 2003;35(4):347-58.
46. Finnigan G, Hanson-Smith V, Stevens T, Thornton J. Evolution of increased complexity in a molecular machine. *Nature* 2012; 481: 360–364.
47. Marshansky V, Futai M. The V-type H⁺-ATPase in vesicular trafficking: targeting, regulation and function. *Curr Opin Cell Biol*. 2008;20(4):415-26.
48. Toei M, Saum R, Forgac M. Regulation and isoform function of the V-ATPases. *Biochemistry*. 2010; 49(23):4715-23.
49. Sun-Wada GH, Wada Y. Vacuolar-type proton pump ATPases: roles of subunit isoforms in physiology and pathology. *Histol Histopathol*. 2010; 25(12):1611-20.
50. Monk BC, Perlin DS. Fungal plasma membrane proton pumps as promising new antifungal targets. *Crit Rev Microbiol*. 1994; 20(3):209-23.
51. Siavoshi F. Comparison of the effect of nonantifungal and antifungal agents on *Candida* isolates from the gastrointestinal tract. *Archives of Iranian medicine* 2012; 15: 27.
52. World Health Organization. Global Tuberculosis Report 2014 WHO (2014). http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/10665/137094/1/9789241564809_eng.pdf?ua=1 accessed on 10/10/2016.
53. Ko Y, Cho I. Putative 3D Structure of QcrB from *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* Cytochrome bc₁ Complex, a Novel Drug-Target for New Series of Antituberculosis Agent Q203. *Bulletin of the Korean Chemical Society*. 2016; 37: 725–731.
54. Abrahams KA, Cox JAG, Spivey VL, Loman NJ, Pallen MJ, Constantinidou C, et al. Identification of Novel Imidazo [1,2-a] pyridine Inhibitors Targeting *M. tuberculosis* QcrB. *PLoS ONE* 2012; 7(12): e52951.
55. Birth D, Kao WC, Hunte C. Structural analysis of atovaquone-inhibited cytochrome bc₁ complex reveals the molecular basis of antimalarial drug action. *Nat Commun*. 2014; 5: 4029.
56. Derbyshire ER, Prudêncio M, Mota MM, Clardy J. Liver-stage malaria parasites vulnerable to diverse chemical scaffolds. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2012;109(22):8511-6.
57. Jonkers D, Stobberingh E, Stockbrugger R. Omeprazole inhibits growth of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria including *Helicobacter pylori* in vitro. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy* 1996; 37: 145-150.
58. Ling R, Luckey M. Use of single-cysteine mutants to probe the location of the disulfide bond in LamB protein from *Escherichia coli*. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*. 1994; 201(1):242-7.